

How to Find and Access data in Europe

A practical introduction - WORKSHOP

Irena Vipavc Brvar, ADP and Jennifer Buckley, UKDS

Overview

1. Data types and sources
2. Identify what you need
3. Searching data archives
4. Evaluating data: quality and usefulness
5. Accessing data

Practical activities

⇒ find and evaluate the usefulness of data for a specific research question

1 Data types and sources

Activity 1

Your knowledge and experience of the data landscape

List

- types and sources of data you know
- how you have/might use archived data

<https://wall2.sli.do/event/g8xaftqc>

Types of data

Thinking about the types of data available can help you work out what you need and how to find it.

Quantitative and Qualitative

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

Types of data: level of analysis

Macro data

- Aggregate
 - about populations, groups, regions and countries constructed by combining information on lower level units (e.g. unemployment rate, fertility)
- System level
 - characteristics of higher-level units such as the state or the political system e.g. electoral system (PR or single-member districts) and member of EU

Meso data

- data on collective and cooperative actors such as commercial companies, organizations or political parties

Microdata

- data from individual units (often people or households) often from surveys, a census and administrative records

Types of data: time

Cross-sectional

- one-point of time (a snap shot)
- usually information on multiple cases and variables

Repeated cross sectional

- cross-sectional surveys repeated with new samples
- data from the different samples allows analysis of trends

Time series

- series of data points in time order (often equally spaced in time)
- aggregate macro data are often time-series data.
- time points may come from sample surveys e.g. unemployment from labour force surveys

Longitudinal

- follow the same units over time e.g. household panel studies collect information from a sample of households in regular 'waves'

Sources of data

There are many sources of data

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

cessda eric

Sources of data: European social science data archives

SND Swedish National Data Service

Data collections include:

- variation between archives
- quantitative data - major source of individual level data
- qualitative
- outputs of
 - major academic projects
 - government/policy
 - small research teams
 - individual researchers
- recent and less recent data
- different languages

cessda eric

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

*"enabling the research
community to conduct high-
quality research in the social
science"*

Key tasks

- Developing standards and best practices
- Facilitating access to important data resources

➤ Work done by developing tools, training and co-ordinating network

CESSDA About

Members

- » Austria
- » Belgium
- » Czech Republic
- » Denmark
- » France
- » Finland
- » Germany
- » Greece
- » Hungary
- » Netherlands
- » Norway
- » Portugal
- » Slovakia
- » Slovenia
- » Sweden
- » *Switzerland*
- » UK

National data services

Activities include

- checking the quality of data and metadata
- maintaining catalogues
- managing access to data through appropriate licensing
- obtaining data
- training for both those creating and using data

Open Access to research data (European Commission)

Open access (OA) can be defined as the practice of providing on-line access to scientific information that is free of charge to the user and that is re-usable. Open access to 'scientific information' refers to two main categories:

Peer-reviewed scientific publications (primarily research articles published in academic journals)

Scientific research data: data underlying publications and/or other data (such as curated but unpublished datasets or raw data)

AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE, AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY

Source

cessda eric

HOW IT WORKS

 #openaccess
#opendata
#H2020

Source: EC

Open Access to research data

-> importance of research infrastructures / data repositories

Source: EC

cessda eric

Horizon Europe

2021-2027

Reinforce openness

Open Science will become the modus operandi of Horizon Europe. It will go beyond the open access policy of Horizon 2020 and require open access to publications, data, and to research data management plans.

Source: EC

cessda eric

Slovenian Social Science Data Archives (ADP)

- Founded in 1997
- Slovenian national data repository for social sciences
- 600 social science surveys with data in a data catalogue + 150 with metadata
- Cca. 800 users registered in 2017 (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- 168 survey data used for detailed secondary-analysis in 2017

- Oldest data sets in the archive (public opinion polls) are from 1966
- Wide range of topics covered
- In most cases data relates only to Slovenia / few international
- Metadata in SI en EN, Datafiles mostly in SI

UK Data Service

Access to the UK's largest collection of social, economic and population data
Support for users with training and guidance.

- ❑ major UK and cross-national surveys
- ❑ longitudinal studies (household panel and cohort studies)
- ❑ UK Census 1971-2011
- ❑ qualitative data collections
- ❑ research data in a researcher repository (Reshare)

Cross-national studies

International survey research programmes include many European countries

-
- International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)
 - European Social Survey
 - European Values Survey
 - Eurobarometer
 - Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement Europe (SHARE)
 - Generations and gender programme (GGP)

Cross-national studies

International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)

- annual programme (started in 1984)
- cross-national collaboration
- rotating thematic modules e.g.
 - Citizenship: 2004 and 2014
 - Work Orientations: 1989, 1997, 2005, 2015
 - Role of Government: 1985, 1990, 1996, 2006, 2016

Data Download

[Data Catalogue](#)

gesis
Leibniz-Institut
für Sozialwissenschaften

cessda eric

Cross-national studies

Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement Europe (SHARE)

- longitudinal study
- more than 123,000 individuals aged 50
- 27 European countries and Israel
- health, socio-economic status and social and family networks

Select Country

Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe

Home

Organisation

Data Access

Data Documentation

Special Data Sets

SHARE Publications

Press & News

Contact

You are here: Home

SHARE - Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe

The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) is a multidisciplinary and cross-national panel database of micro data on health, socio-economic status and social and family networks of approximately 123,000 individuals aged 50 or older (more than 293,000 interviews). SHARE covers **27 European countries and Israel**.

The **data** are available to the entire research community **free of charge**. For a summary overview and research results of SHARE, you can download the **SHARE brochure** or our latest First Results Book: **Ageing in Europe - Supporting Policies for an Inclusive Society**.

Search

search

News

Wave 6 data released!

SHARE is very happy to announce the release of Wave 6 data! Wave 6 not only includes Croatia as a...

[read more...](#)

Launch of the Executive Master's Programme in Management of Research Infrastructures

Rltrain, the Research Infrastructure Training Programme, is launching its Executive Master's...

[read more...](#)

SHARE Newsletter No. 20

Please enjoy reading our Newsletter No. 20. In this edition, we present to you three of our new...

[read more...](#)

Newsletter

Latest Newsletter

Subscribe to the SHARE newsletter by sending an e-mail to info@share-project.org

Cross-national studies

European Social Survey (ESS)

- A biennial cross-national survey (started in 2002)
- Highest methodological standard

	R1 2002	R2 2004	R3 2006	R4 2008	R5 2010	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016
Media and social trust	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Politics	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Subjective well-being...	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Gender, Household	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Socio demographics	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Human values	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Immigration	•						•	
Citizen involvement	•							
Health and care		•						
Economic morality		•						
Family work and well-being		•			•			

freely available data for 36 countries.

23 countries in 2016

Probably most used / cited data. 125 T registered users, 89 T data downloads.

Source: ESS

CESSDA ERIC

About ESS

Findings

Methodology

Data and Documentation

Learning

search

Topline Results issue 6 out now

Our report identifies rates of self-diagnosed physical and mental health conditions in 21 European nations.

More...

Social Inequalities in Health and their Determinants

Topline Results from Round 7 of the European Social Survey

Latest news

06/04/17 General Assembly meeting later this month

27/03/17 Madrid to host latest event

24/03/17 ESS presents at European conferences

13/03/17 Roger Jowell Memorial Lecture 2017

Data and Documentation

Data and documentation can be accessed by round (year), by theme or by country. Data are available for download and online analysis.

Methodological Research

The European Social Survey runs a programme of research to support and enhance the methodology that underpins the high standards it pursues in every aspect of survey design, data collection and archiving.

Examples: Longitudinal studies

Household panel studies

following households over time and asking questions on a broad range of topics such as household composition, employment, earnings, health, social and political participation and life-satisfaction

- German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP)
- Understanding society (and the British Household Panel Study)
- Swiss Household Panel

Five key data providing organisations

-
- 1 Eurostat – Statistics office of European Union
 - 2 LIS - harmonised socio-economic micro datasets
 - 3 OECD – key source of comparable statistical, economic and social data
 - 4 World Bank - Free and open access to global development data
 - 5 IMF - time series data on economic and financial indicators

Example data provider

Eurostat

Statistical office of the European Union

Provides national and sub-national data

- economy and finance, population and social conditions, industry, trade, agriculture and fisheries, transport, environment and energy and science, technology and innovation

Microdata.

- e.g European Community Household Panel, European Union Labour Force Survey, European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions

Metadata for Official Statistics

MISSY (**Microdata Information System**) is an online service platform that provides structured metadata for official statistics. MISSY includes metadata at the study and variable level as well as reports and tools for data handling and analysis. All documentation in MISSY refers to microdata available for scientific purposes. MISSY currently documents the following official statistics microdata:

EU-Data

- [AES](#) (Adult Education Survey)
- [CIS](#) (Community Innovation Survey)
- [EU-LFS](#) (European Union Labour Force Survey)
- [EU-SILC](#) (European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions)
- [SES](#) (Structure of Earnings Survey)

National Data

- [MZ](#) (German microcensus)

Microcensus (DE)

EU-Data

AES

CIS

EU-LFS

EU-SILC

Browse ▲

2016 2015 2014 2013

2012 2011 2010 2009

2008 2007 2006 2005

Cross-sectional

Select Variable List

Original Order	Thematic Order
Matrix ▼	
Setups	
Materials ▼	
Tools ▼	

Study: EU-SILC 2016

- Titles ▼
- Abstract ▼
- Coverage ▼
- Notes ▼
- References ▼

Country Specific Information: EU-SILC 2016

AT	BE	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL/GR	ES	FI	FR	HR
HU	LT	LV	NL	NO	PL	PT	RO	RS	SE	SI	SK	UK

SI - Slovenia

- National Reference ▼
- Target Sample Size ▼
- Available Data ▼
- Sampling Procedure ▼
- Panel Design ▼
- Data Collection ▼

Source: [MISSY](#)

Series and studies for SLOVENIA	
	Census
	Central Population Register (CPR)
	Community Innovation Survey (CIS)
	European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)
	External Trade
	Final accounts
	Graduates in tertiary education
	Gross Fixed Capital Formation
	Household Budget Survey (HBS)
	Industrial production
	Labour Force Survey (LFS)
	Personal Income Tax
	Slovenian Business Register
	Statistical Register of Employment
	Student enrolment in tertiary education
	Time Use Survey (TUS)
	Unemployed workers
	Usage of information-communication technologies in enterprises
	Victimisation Survey (VS)

Factsheet: Accreditation & Data Access Conditions for SLOVENIA

Contact

Name

Statistični urad Republike Slovenije (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, SORS)

Postal Address

Litostrojska cesta 54 SI-1000 Ljubljana (Slovenia)

Contact

info.stat@gov.si

Website

[\[click here\]](#)

CIMES

Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics

Conditions

General Conditions

Microdata can be provided for research purposes to registered research institutions and registered researchers in both academia and government offices. "Registered" researchers have a national identifier. As a general rule, users submit applications for access that are assessed by a Confidentiality committee (internal to SORS); the latter prepares recommendations for SORS's board of directors, which makes the final decision.

Conditions for Non-Resident Researchers

Same as national researchers (though requests from non-registered researchers should be evaluated by the internal Confidentiality committee).

Source: [CIMES](#)

	Series and studies for SLOVENIA	X
	Census	
	Central Population Register (CPR)	
	Community Innovation Survey (CIS)	
	European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)	
	External Trade	
	Final accounts	
	Graduates in tertiary education	
	Gross Fixed Capital Formation	
	Household Budget Survey (HBS)	
	Industrial production	
	Labour Force Survey (LFS)	
	Labour Force Survey - 1995	
	Labour Force Survey - 1996	
	Labour Force Survey - 1997	
	Labour Force Survey - 1998	
	Labour Force Survey - 1999	
	Labour Force Survey - 2000	
	Labour Force Survey - 2001	
	Labour Force Survey - 2002	
	Labour Force Survey - 2003	
	Labour Force Survey - 2004	
	Labour Force Survey - 2005	
	Labour Force Survey - 2006	
	Labour Force Survey - 2007	
	Labour Force Survey - 2008	
	Labour Force Survey - 2009	

Study

Labour Force Survey - 2011

Original Title :

Anketa o delovni sili - 2011

Original Alternative Title :

ADS - 2011

English Alternative Title:

LFS - 2011

Producer : SORS.

Abstract :

Slovenian Labour Force Survey 2011 is a Slovenian research with a tradition. The LFS measures the labour status and other characteristics of the population in a certain week of each quarter, by spreading the sample uniformly over all the weeks of the quarter. The survey provides data on size, structure and characteristics of active and inactive population. Data on personal income are added to the dataset (DURS register) – an average monthly income in either the whole year or a shorter period of time, if a person had worked for less than a year. Approximately 19.750 individuals are selected to the sample in each quarter. Non-anonymised version of LFS microdata is available to researchers, onsite or by remote access. The survey was conducted as one of the surveys of the Eurostat Labour Force Survey which includes data from 27 Member States of the European Union, four Candidate Countries and two EFTA countries (Norway and Switzerland). Comparability through time and space is possible as Eurostat distributes Labour Force Survey data of other participating countries.

Keywords :

LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS

Geographic coverage : Slovenia.

Universe :

The target population is the jure population, which includes persons that are mainly living in the territory of Republic of Slovenia, regardless of their nationality. Only the population, is living in individual households, is covered by the survey. Institutionalized people are not considered as a part of the jure population. Those who live in institutions (soldiers, hospitalized, imprisoned etc.) for more than 12 months, including students who don't live at home and Slovenian citizens who live abroad permanently or temporarily, are not covered by the survey.

Sampling Procedure :

The Labour Force Survey is based on the sample taken from the Central Population Register. It is a rotating panel carried out continuously throughout the whole year. The sampling method is stratified systematic random sampling of addresses. All members of the household at the selected address are included in the sample. That means that there are approximately 16 150 individuals included in each

CIMES

Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics

Source: [CIMES](#)

ssda eric

Direct from project websites

Some research projects share research data through project websites

<http://cwed2.org/>

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset (CWED). The header features the CWED logo (three circles and the text 'CWED Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset') and three institutional logos: the University of Cambridge, the University of Oxford, and a blue circular logo. A red navigation bar contains the following links: Home, About, Data, People, Publications, Working Paper Series, FAQs, and Links. The main content area includes a 'WELCOME' section with a paragraph describing the dataset, a 'Principal Investigators' box listing Lyle Scruggs, Kati Kuitto, and Detlef Jahn, and a link to 'Download CWED 2 data here'. A 'NEWS' section at the bottom lists two items: 'Updated list of scientific works and papers is available' (dated June 22, 2017) and 'Forthcoming publications from CWED members' (dated June 09, 2017).

CWED
Comparative
Welfare
Entitlements
Dataset

UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE
UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD

Home About Data People Publications Working Paper Series FAQs Links

WELCOME

The Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset (CWED) contains information about the structure and generosity of social insurance benefits in 33 countries around the world. Since September 2017, an updated version of CWED 2 containing a total of **eight household types** is available. The data contained here are an updated and extended version of CWED 1, which has been available since 2004.

This web site allows you to download customized portions of the CWED 2 data, browse the Working Paper Series or access documentary material.

[Download CWED 2 data here](#)

Principal Investigators:
Lyle Scruggs
Kati Kuitto
Detlef Jahn

NEWS

June 22, 2017 **Updated list of scientific works and papers is available**
More than 200 peer-reviewed scientific works are using CWED2 data. You can access an updated of all books, papers, and chapters in edited volumes using our dataset [here](#).

June 09, 2017 **Forthcoming publications from CWED members**

Data repositories

Digital archives collecting, preserving and displaying datasets, related documentation and metadata.

Types of repository

domain-specific trusted repositories (e.g. CESSDA archives) - focus on high-quality data with a potential for reuse

institutional research data repositories e.g. universities

general purpose repositories e.g. Zenodo, Figshare, Harvard Dataverse

cessda eric

A registry of research data repositories.

Search

- ✓ by subject, content type and country
- ✓ for data archives with a certificate (a trusted repository), open access or for data sets that have a persistent identifier

2. Identify what you need

Four ways we can use archived data

New analysis: one or multiple data sources e.g. combine micro and macro, just secondary data or secondary data combined with primary data

Replication

Use of study design/methodology (e.g. data collection tools (interview schedules & survey questions) or sampling strategies)

Teaching : Subject-based or research methods,
Datasets made for training purposes – e.g. easySHARE

Identifying data needs

Research Question

- What is the ideal dataset for addressing this question?

(Compromises needed in reality)

Key concepts

How to operationalise?

(concepts can be complex and difficult to measure)

- Key features
- Multidimensional
- Groups of people
- Dependent/
independent variables

- What key features
- Multiple variables?
- Comparable/established measures (e.g. Schwarz Human Values)
- Standardised (e.g. ILO unemployment, ISCO, ESeC)

Identifying data needs

Activity 2

Identify data needs

Task: identify data needs - Evaluating data worksheet

3. Searching data archives

Three types of search

1. Search for data on a topic
2. Search for a specific dataset
3. Browse data collections by type or theme

Online catalogues – searching (browsing)

language

Search on site | På svenska

SND Swedish National Data Service

FIND AND ORDER DATA DATA MANAGEMENT DESCRIBE AND DEPOSIT DATA SND EVENTS ABOUT US

Order data SND Online Analysis Collections Data in Focus International data Questions & variables Accessibility levels

Home / Find and order data

Site map

Find and order data

Filter/sort

Filter

- Kind of data
- Subject
- Principal
- Funding agency
- Availability status
- Series
- Geographic location

political attitudes

SEARCH

247 hits

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 .. 24 25 Next

[Socio-political attitudes 1975](#)

Stockholm University

The central aim of the study is looking at various aspects of political perception as a function of socio-political ideology. The politically perceived objects consists mainly of political parties, party-leaders and c...

▪ Bo Ekehammar, Stockholm University, Department of Psychology

Published: 1987

1C

[Socio-political attitudes 1979](#)

Stockholm University

The aim of the study is basically the same as in Socio-Political Attitudes 1975. In the

ADP - SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVES

Analyze data! Deposit study! Promote science!

Subscribe to eNews

eNews Blog Contact FAQ SLO

Home | USE DATA | DEPOSIT STUDY | LEARN ABOUT | DISCOVER ADP | SEARCH

- List of studies by:
- Study ID
 - Series
 - Study topics
 - Depositors
 - Year of Production
 - Year of Publication
 - Author
 - International studies

Use data / ADP Catalogue

ADP CATALOGUE

Date of the last change of the catalog: 06.07.2018

List of studies by study's ID

Study ID	Study title, topic	Access
EUVET12	7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries topic: EDUCATION, EDUCATION - vocational education, produced by: COI	nesstor
EWCS05	European Working Conditions Survey 2005 topic: LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT - employment, produced by: EUROFOUND	nesstor
EWCS01	Working Conditions in European Union Candidate Countries, 2001 topic: LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT - employment, produced by: EUROFOUND	nesstor
FEMAKT16	Intersectionality and Feminist Activism, 2016: Student Feminist Societies in the United Kingdom topic: SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS, SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS - gender and gender roles, produced by: None	nesstor

Study Topics

- DEMOGRAPHY, POPULATION, VITAL STATISTICS AND CENSUSES
- [ECONOMICS](#)
- EDUCATION
- HEALTH
- HOUSING AND LAND USE PLANNING
- INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
- LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
- LAW, CRIME AND LEGAL SYSTEMS
- NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- Not categorized
- OTHER
- POLITICS
- PSYCHOLOGY
- SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS
- SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE
- TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MARKETS
- TRANSPORT, TRAVEL AND MOBILITY

Economic Morality (ESS2 2004)

Data/Variables - Round 2 (2004)

- i** Citizens should spend some free time helping others
- i** Society better off if everyone looked after themselves
- i** Citizens should not cheat on taxes
- i** Trust plumber/builder/mechanic/other repairer deal honestly with you
- i** Trust financial companies/bank/insurers deal honestly with you
- i** Trust public officials deal honestly with you
- i** Plumber/builder/mechanic/repairer overcharged you, how often last 5 years
- i** You were sold food packed to conceal worse bits, how often last 5 years
- i** Bank/insurance company failed to offer best deal, how often last 5 years
- i** You were sold things second-hand that proved faulty, how often last 5 years
- i** Public official asked favour/bribe for service, how often last 5 years
- i** How worried are you of being treated dishonestly
- i** Someone paying cash without receipt to avoid VAT or tax, how wrong

Source: [ESS](#)

Documentation often extensive

ESS Rounds

[ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

[ESS Round 3 \(2006\)](#)

[ESS Round 2 \(2004\)](#)

[ESS Round 1 \(2002\)](#)

ESS8 - 2016 Data Download

The ESS8-2016 Edition 1.1 was released on 9th of April 2018. Please see [Version notes](#) for complete information.

Users are obliged to read the [ESS conditions of use](#). Please see [Deviations in data](#) for an overview of errors or deviations in different countries.

ESS8 - integrated file
Edition 1.1

Integrated files and documents

[ESS8 - integrated file, edition 1.1](#)

[ESS8 - data from Interviewer's questionnaire, edition 1.0](#)

[ESS8 - test data \(MTMM\), edition 1.0](#)

[ESS8 - data from Contact forms, edition 2.0](#)

[ESS8 - data from Media claims, edition 1.0](#)

[Guide to weighting of ESS data](#)

[FAQ: Combining data files, Renaming variables, Other data formats.](#)

[Fieldwork Summary and Deviations](#)

Survey Documentation

[ESS8 Data Documentation Report ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A1 Education ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A2 Income ed. 1.0](#)

ESS Findings

Findings from the European Social Survey are available in a number of publications.

[>>](#)

ESS Data Alerts

[ESS8 Swedish data removed - 09/04/18](#)

[ESS7 Error in INWMME and INWYYE for Netherlands - 12/02/18](#)

[ESS8 Error in INWMMS and INWYYS for Netherlands - 24/01/18](#)

[ESS8 Second edition \(2.0\) of Contact form data - 15/12/17](#)

Questions?

Questions regarding data or documentation, please contact essdatasupport@nsd.no

Integrated File – Download

[Download ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

NESSTAR for online browsing and analysis

The screenshot shows the ESS DATA website interface. At the top, there is a red header with the European Social Survey logo on the left, 'ESS DATA' in the center, and 'NORWEGIAN SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA SERVICES NSD' on the right. Below the header is a navigation bar with tabs for 'DESCRIPTION', 'TABULATION', and 'ANALYSIS'. The 'DESCRIPTION' tab is active, showing the title 'European Social Survey (2017). ESS Round 8 (2016/2017) Technical Report. London: ESS ERIC'. Below the title, there is a 'List of Keywords' section with a bulleted list: Trust, politics, social values, social exclusion, discrimination, religion, national identity, climate change, energy, and welfare. There is also a 'Topic Classification' section with a bulleted list: Social trust, political interest and participation, socio-political orientations, social exclusion, national, ethnic and religious allegiances, climate change, energy security and energy preferences, welfare, human values, and demographics and socioeconomics. On the left side, there is a sidebar with a tree view of the site structure, including 'ESS', 'Metadata', 'Study Description', 'Variable Description', and 'Country'. The 'Country' section is expanded, showing a list of countries: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russian Federation, Slovenia, and Sweden.

- online data browsing and analysis
- download tables, graphs, data files and study descriptions
- main catalogue or additional tool
- help pages [? at top]

Let's start with a simple exercise comparing **life satisfaction measures** of two groups – the **unemployed people looking for work** versus **people in paid work**. Calculate the means for the two groups across Europe.

Variable mnactic: Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded

LITERAL QUESTION

F17c2. POST CODE: I

Values	Categories	Code	Frequency	% of all	% of valid
	Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded				
1	Paid work	1	25,760	47.1	47.6
2	Education	2	4,704	8.6	8.7
3	Unemployed, looking for job	3	2,978	5.4	5.5
4	Unemployed, not looking for job	4	1,155	2.1	2.1
5	Permanently sick or disabled	5	1,291	2.4	2.4
6	Retired	6	12,819	23.4	23.7
7	Community or military service	7	90	0.2	0.2
8	Housework, looking after children, others	8	4,796	8.8	8.9
9	Other	9	520	1.0	1.0
66	Not applicable				
77	Refusal	77	39	0.1	-
88	Don't know	88	105	0.2	-
99	No answer	99	416	0.8	-
	Total		54,673	100.0	100.0

SUMMARY STATISTICS

This variable is numerical

Socio-demographics

- Doing last 7 days: no answer
- Interviewer code, one/more than one doing last 7 days
- Main activity last 7 days
- Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post code
- Interviewer code, respondent in p
- Control paid work last 7 days
- Ever had a paid job
- Year last in paid job
- Employment relation
- Number of employees respondent
- Employment contract unlimited or limited duration
- Establishment size

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

DESCRIPTION TABULATION ANALYSIS

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Choose 'Add to column' to place the variable here.

To populate this table you need to select a variable from the browse list, click on it and then add it to row, column or layers, or use it as a measure variable.

Politics

- Placement on left right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national g
- How satisfied with the way demo
- State of education in country now
- State of health services in countr
- Government should reduce differences in income levels
- Gays and lesbians free to live life as they wish

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

B20. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

	Median	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Sum	Count
Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded							
Paid work	7.5	7.0	0.0	10.0	2.2	179,423.0	25,653
Education	8.0	7.7	0.0	10.0	1.9	35,885.0	4,676
Unemployed, looking for job	5.6	5.4	0.0	10.0	2.7	16,028.0	2,956
Unemployed, not looking for job	5.7	5.6	0.0				
Permanently sick or disabled	5.6	5.5	0.0				
Retired	7.0	6.5	0.0				
Community or military service	7.6	6.9	0.0				
Housework, looking after children, others	7.2	6.6	0.0				
Other	7.6	7.0	0.0				
Total	7.30	6.76	0.00				

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Main activity, la...dents. Post coded		
All		
✓ Categories		
Change selection...		
Move to column		
Use as Filter		
Remove from table		
Insert calculation		
Permanently sick or disabled	5.6	5.5
Retired	7.0	6.5
Community or military service	7.6	6.9

Change selection

Search for categories

All

Paid work

Education

Unemployed, looking for job

Unemployed, not looking for job

Permanently sick or disabled

Retired

Community or military service

Housework, looking after children, others

Other

OK

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

FINDING DATA

ADVANCED SEARCH

Advanced Search - Mozilla Firefox

zocat.gesis.org/webview/velocity?mode=searchview&searchtype=advanced&&

Advanced Search

Search criteria:

Variable contains health

Search for: datasets variables

SEARCH

Study Description

- Study Description
- Bibliographic Citation
- Title Statement
- Full Title
- Identification Number
- Responsibility Statement
- Authoring Entity
- Production Statement
- Producer
- Copyright
- Funding Agency/Sponsor
- Distributor Statement
- Data Distributor
- Abbreviation
- Depositor
- Study Scope
- Subject Information
- List of Keywords
- Topic Classification
- Abstract

EVS 2008: Belgium
EVS 2008: Greece
EVS 2008: Integrated Dataset
EVS 2008: Estonia
EVS 2008: Portugal
EVS 2008: Lithuania
describe your state of health these days (Q4)
do you belong to: voluntary health organisations (Q5aN)
how much confidence in: health care system (Q63M)
do you work unpaid for: voluntary health organisations (Q5bN)
kind of job respondent - ISCO88 code (Q112)
kind of job spouse/partner - ISCO88 code (Q118)
kind of job father/mother - ISCO88 code (Q129a)
EVS 2008: Turkey
EVS 2008: Azerbaijan
International Social Survey Programme: Social Inequality

ZA4768: EVS 2008: Lithuania
[ZA4768 Datafiles and Documentation download](#) (via data catalogue)

Variable v9: describe your state of health these days (Q4)

LITERAL QUESTION

Q4
<SHOW CARD 4>
All in all, how would you describe your state of health these days? Would you say it is

-5 other missing
-4 question not asked
-3 nap
-2 na
-1 dk
1 very good
2 good
3 fair
4 poor
5 very poor

CESSDA data catalogue

Coming
Summer 2018

Search data collection of
all CESSDA members

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://datacatalogue-dev.cessda.eu>. The page header includes the CESSDA logo and the text "Find Social and Economic Research Data". Below the header, it indicates "7163 results found in 20ms". The search results are displayed in a list format. The first result is titled "National Opinion Polls National Political Surveys; 2-7 July 1974" by "NOP Market Research Limited". The abstract for this result reads: "Abstract copyright UK Data Service and data collection copyright owner. The NOP National Political Surveys are conducted by NOP on a regular basis. These surveys are designed principally to ascertain public opinion on political parties, leaders and government, and to record voting intention. Data of this nature are given for each survey. In addition, the majority of surveys present data of topical interest and of social importance. +Main Topics: Variables Topics covered in the past include: Vot...". The second result is titled "Disability Follow-Up to the 1996/97 Family Resources Survey" by the "Department of Social Security. Social Research Branch". Its abstract reads: "Abstract copyright UK Data Service and data collection copyright owner. The aim of the survey was to find out the size and characteristics of the disabled adult population of GB. The research is based on a follow-up survey of disabled respondents in Family Resources Survey, 1996-1997, held under SN 3957 - part of a continuous survey of household characteristics, incomes and resources. Respondents who matched any one of a series of sift criteria based on age, benefit receipt or reported health...". A search filter menu is open, showing options for "Relevance", "Title (ascending)", "Title (descending)", "Date of collection (ascending)", and "Date of collection (descending)".

Finding data in practice

Searching can be hard

- Too many results
- No results
- Results not relevant

Evaluate search terms

- How well do they relate to your data needs?
- Spelling/language
- “Exact terms”, Boolean Logic (AND OR) – check how search tool works

Sort, filter, advance search

ELSST

Multilingual thesaurus of social science concepts

Hierarchical and non-hierarchical relationships between concepts

Use to

- broaden or narrow a search
- find terms used to index data in other languages

In future, ELSST will be used more widely to index data & embedded within search tool

elsst.ukdataservice.ac.uk

cessda eric

Activity 3

Searching for data

Finding data sources to examine ideas about cultural backlash

Task A

Use ELSST to select search terms

- <https://elsst.ukdataservice.ac.uk/>
- Find related, broaden or narrow search terms
- Terms in other languages

Task B

Search for data using a data catalogue

- Any national data service
- See CESSDA for links:
www.cessda.eu/Consortium

4. Evaluating data: quality and usefulness

The longer process

Research design (data management plans)

Consider the previous processes to assess data quality and suitability

- What information was collected, from whom, when and where?
- What has been done to the resulting data?

Metadata and documentation

Metadata ("data about data")

- descriptors that facilitate cataloguing data and data discovery.

Documentation

- user guides, survey questionnaires, interview schedules and fieldwork notes

- Catalogue records (with links to documentation)
- Quality can vary
- Efforts to improve data documentation
- Check for helpdesks/training

cessda eric

What to look for when assessing quality?

Can I establish

- Why the data was created
- What the dataset contains
- How data was collected
- Who collected the data and when
- How was the data processed
- Any manipulations done to the data
- What quality assurance procedures were used

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

But is it useful?

Ask how it compares to your ideal dataset

- key concepts
- population
- geographical area
- time period
- units of analysis
- study/sample design

Activity 4

Evaluating data chosen

Evaluate the usefulness of found data
See worksheet

5. Accessing data

*“Now finally, I’ve found some great data,
how to I get it”*

- Licenses
- Access process
- Getting started

Data access arrangements 1

Open data

any user, no registering
(acknowledge source)

Registration

- often with institutional user name and password
- may wait for user name or password
- register use of data

Terms and conditions

- not trying to identify individuals, households or organisations
- not distributing data to others
- "data is for non-commercial use only" or for "use in research or teaching" only.

Download

from catalogue (but sometimes complete a request form)

Data access arrangements 2

- ❑ Sometimes permission from the data owners required (= a additional stage)
- ❑ Sensitive or confidential data = more strict (and lengthy) process
- ❑ Some services operate a dedicated safe room or safe access service
- ❑ Access by users outside the country can be prohibited for confidential data
- ❑ Free (except for commercial use and supplementary services)

If you are unsure, ask the relevant data service for help.

Getting started: using project-level and data-level documentation

What you might need to know?

- Folder structures and file names
- Version
- Case summaries
- Variables lists
- Exact question wording
- Questionnaire routing
- Manipulations to data and coding
- Weights
- Missing data
- Contextual details

Where to look?

- In a data file (e.g. summary of interview details before transcript, variable and value labels)
- Data lists (e.g. case summaries, variables lists)
- A user guide
- Fieldwork notes
- Technical report
- Readme files/version notes

And finally...remember to cite data

Why?

- It gives credit the data creators
- It makes data easier to find

How?

- Give enough information to locate the exact version of the data
- Look for recommended citation
- Use persistent identifiers (Digital Object Identifier (DOI))

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

Citation requirements

The Core Scientific Team of the ESS requests that references to ESS data and the Data Documentation Reports should use the form of words listed below.

To ensure that such source attributions are captured for social science bibliographic utilities, citations must appear in the footnotes or in the reference section of publications.

Citation of data

- ESS Round 8: European Social Survey Round 8 Data (2016). Data file edition 1.0. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 7: European Social Survey Round 7 Data (2014). Data file edition 2.1. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 6: European Social Survey Round 6 Data (2012). Data file edition 2.3. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 5: European Social Survey Round 5 Data (2010). Data file edition 3.3. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 4: European Social Survey Round 4 Data (2008). Data file edition 4.4. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 3: European Social Survey Round 3 Data (2006). Data file edition 3.6. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 2: European Social Survey Round 2 Data (2004). Data file edition 3.5. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.
- ESS Round 1: European Social Survey Round 1 Data (2002). Data file edition 6.5. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC.

Citation of documentation

- ESS Round 8: European Social Survey (2017): ESS-8 2016 Documentation Report. Edition 1.0. Bergen, European Social Survey Data Archive, NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data for ESS ERIC.

are available in a number of publications.
>>

ESS Data Alerts

ESS8 Swedish data removed - 09/04/18

ESS7 Error in INWMME and INWYYE for Netherlands - 12/02/18

ESS8 Error in INWMMS and INWYYS for Netherlands - 24/01/18

ESS8 Second edition (2.0) of Contact form data - 15/12/17

Questions?

Questions regarding data or documentation, please contact essdatasupport@nsd.no

Integrated File – Download

[Download ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 3 \(2006\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 2 \(2004\)](#)

[Download ESS Round 1 \(2002\)](#)

Online Analysis

[Open ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[Open ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

ELEMENTS OF DATA CITATION

- **Author:** Name(s) of each individual or organizational entity responsible for the creation of the dataset.
- **Date of Publication:** Year the dataset was published or disseminated.
- **Title:** Complete title of the dataset, including the edition or version number, if applicable.
- **Publisher and/or Distributor:** Organizational entity that makes the dataset available by archiving, producing, publishing, and/or distributing the dataset.
- **Electronic Location or Identifier:** Web address or unique, persistent, global identifier used to locate the dataset (such as a DOI). Append the date retrieved if the title and locator are not specific to the exact instance of the data you used.

These are the minimum elements required for dataset identification and retrieval. Fewer or additional elements may be requested by author guidelines or style manuals. Be sure to include as many elements as needed to precisely identify the dataset you have used.

Source: [IASSIST – Quick guide to Data Citation](#)

ISSP Research Group (2017): International Social Survey Programme: Work Orientations IV - ISSP 2015. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA6770 Data file Version 2.1.0, doi:10.4232/1.12848

Hafner-Fink, M. and Malešič, M. (2016). Slovenian Public Opinion 2015: Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of public opinion and National Security Survey [Data file]. Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana, Social Science Data Archives. ADP – IDNO: SJM15. Accessible at: <https://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/sjm15/>

Questions

*Pictures from
CESSDA Training Working Group (2017). CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC.*